

1 SLBP, the stem loop binding protein, has a critical function during transformation of human cells.

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7 We describe here the function of a molecule known as the stem loop binding protein, SLBP, in
8 transformation *in vivo* and *in vitro*. SLBP was an important and essential component of the gene signature
9 of early transformation *in vivo* when studying neoplasia in the human vulva. SLBP induction occurred
10 early in transformation concurrent with activation of *HELLS* and *CDT1*, DNA damage repair protein
11 *RAD51AP1*, an Xist repair pathway adapter protein *UHRF1*, and epigenetic enzymes *EZH2* and *DNMT1*.
12 SLBP was activated by mutation of *MRE11A* or *H2AX*, indicating its relative position in biological functions
13 relevant to the relationship between DNA damage and transformation. Importantly, SLBP expression was
14 silenced in *ATM* knockout cells. SLBP induction during transformation and temporal dynamics in neoplasia
15 *in vivo* indicate an important transcriptional function for SLBP in transformation.
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